

Reducing gas sensing property of polypyrrole/polyaniline conducting polymer blends synthesized by interfacial polymerization

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Abstract

Polypyrrole/Polyaniline conducting polymer blends as room temperature operated hydrogen gas sensor were fabricated using simple inexpensive Interfacial Polymerization method. Synthesis of polypyrrole and polyaniline conducting polymers were achieved by the interfacial polymerization. Miscible and Immiscible conducting polymer blends were synthesized by one step and two step polymerization methods respectively (1, 2). The Glass Transition Temperature (T_g) of the conducting polymer blends were determined by Thermo gravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). Surface morphological studies were characterized by the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM). Structural studies were done by the X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and UV-visible absorption Spectroscopy. The polymer blends showed selectivity towards hydrogen among oxygen and Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG). It also revealed improved sensor characteristics such as sensitivity, response time and recovery time. The fabricated electrodes are highly stable for the period of 50 days.

Key Words: Polypyrrole/Polyaniline Blends, Interfacial Polymerization, Hydrogen Gas, Sensitivity

References

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